

INTERACTION BETWEEN AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY

1. Newly planted maize. Poplar plantation, Santa Fe Granada 2. Maize planted between the poplar rows, Santa Fe, Granada 3. First year maize, close to harvest, Santa Fe, Granada

THE WHAT AND WHY

The cultivation of poplars in the province of Granada offers a series of benefits ranging from the ecological improvement of the environment to the economic and social promotion of the area. Their ability to adapt to diverse conditions, their contribution to sustainability and their potential as a source of income make poplar trees a valuable option for farmers and the community at large.

The company Agrosericios Hijo de Celedonio S.L., has incorporated the cultivation of maize into the production of poplars. This practice was already carried out in the past in the area of Vega de Granada, which consisted of growing different horticultural products between the poplar groves rows during the first year of production. Nowadays, the industrialisation of production has led to its disappearance in practically the whole area, but some farmers have recovered it and turned it into a productive strategy.

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

On the farm under study, there are currently 125 ha of poplar trees divided into plots of between 10 and 15 ha, where one of the plots is cut each year. At present there are 125 ha of poplar trees divided into plots of between 10 and 15 ha and each year one of the plots is cut down. Poplar trees, which have a 10-year cycle, are planted at the end of February, while maize is sown in mid-April, taking advantage of the humidity provided by the irrigation that the poplar trees receive at this time. At the same time, maize provides essential ground cover for the development of the poplar tree at the beginning of its growth.

In this case, maize is planted in rows, approximately 4 rows of maize per poplar lane, leaving enough space between the poplars to ensure that both crops can grow without competing for light and nutrients.

The area under the tree that remains unproductive accounts for 30% of the area, however, corn yield in the first year of the poplars is 10,000 kg/ha. In the second year, due to the shade provided by the poplar trees, maize yield is reduced to 6,000 kg/ha. The high profitability of maize allows for increased land use efficiency.

Keywords: Maize, poplar, agroforestry, inter-row cultivation

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ADVANTAGES

This system ensures that both crops can grow without competing for light and nutrients. As fast-growing trees, poplars provide shade for maize, which helps to reduce soil temperature and evapotranspiration, thus favouring the development of maize during hot summer days.

This farming model allows farmers to diversify their income. While poplars can be harvested every 10 years for timber production, maize can be harvested annually. This provides a steady stream of income and reduces economic risk.

Planting maize between the poplar rows, as an agroforestry system, offers multiple environmental, economic and agricultural advantages. This system combines agricultural crops with high-value trees, such as poplars, thus optimising the use of space and resources. Land use is improved through the efficient use of space, thus allowing the areas between the rows of poplars that would otherwise be unused, to be used properly. The combination of poplar wood production with maize production has an impact on increasing soil productivity.

This system protects the soil and helps to preserve water, as the roots of poplars stabilise the soil, preventing erosion, especially on sloping terrain. It also helps to preserve moisture, as poplars act as a barrier to reduce water evaporation from the soil, benefiting maize in times of drought. Tree roots improve porosity and nutrient retention in the soil.

With this management, income is diversified. Farmers get their income from both the maize crop and the wood or biomass from the poplar trees, and economic irrigation is minimised by combining the two crops.

This agroforestry system is an interesting option for combining environmental sustainability with agricultural productivity.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Nowadays, the industrialisation of production has led to its disappearance in practically the whole area, but some farmers have recovered it and turned it into a productive strategy.**
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Poplar tree nursery, Santa Fé Granada, year 0

More Information(web):

<https://chopomarjal.es/> <https://life-woodforfuture.eu/>

ANA VICTORIA CAMPOS GALISTEO, LAURA MORENO CARBONELL

Agency for the Management of Agriculture and Fisheries of Andalusia

anav.campos@juntadeandalucia.es

laura.moreno.carbonell@juntadeandalucia.es

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.